

HERITABILITY OF A QUANTITATIVE COTTON TRAIT IN HYBRID
POPULATIONS F₂

M. R. Kodirova

PhD, Institute of Genetics and Plant
Experimental Biology of the Academy Sciences
of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan

kodirova.mohidilhon@mail.ru

Abstract. The article presents analysis of heritability estimate by a raw cotton boll mass in a population of geographically separated cotton F₂ hybrids. Efficacy of selection by a raw cotton boll mass was demonstrated to depend on individual peculiarities of the genotypes hybridized.

Key words: cotton, hybrid, population, heritability, breeding, variety, genotype, biotype, phenotype, individual selection.

Introduction.

Cotton breeding at the final stage is based on selection, which is a continuation of genetic studies, that is, hybridologic analysis of F₁ and F₂ hybrid populations. Analytical selection is based on individual selection from genetically heterogeneous populations of cotton older generation hybrids, lines and cultivars. In natural settings the cultivar heterogeneity results from natural hybridization between genotype populations, natural mutations and their crossing. One and the same culture is known to have various environment dependence traits. Some traits more depend on growth environment; the others are governed by a genotype. Heritability estimate is routinely calculated by fractional value from 0 to 1 or in percent from 0 to 100. The higher the heritability estimate, the stronger is heritable dependence of the trait [5,6]. According to [3], genotypic variance consists of 1) additive genetic variance, 2) dominance related deviation and 3) interaction or epistatic deviation.

Estimates of heritability for various traits, in addition to estimates of their genetic correlations, can be used to identify indirect selection patterns which appear more efficient than the direct selection for trait to be improved [1,2,4]. Thus, as most authors report, heritability estimate is a real value to be used as sustainable method for selection, and prediction of the process efficacy, which is essential for selection process planning.

Quantitative traits of cotton in the second generation have a complex nature of heredity. On the one hand, it is connected with the genetic variability, on the other, with the paratypic one. Paratypic variability makes study on hereditary variability of traits difficult.

Material and research methods

Scientific research was carried out at the experimental station of Institute of Genetics and Experimental Biology of Plants of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, located in Zangiata district, Tashkent region. This territory is located on the upper route of the Chirchik River, at an altitude of 398 meters above sea level. The number of sunny days is 175-185, and the frost-free period is 210 days. Field sowing was carried out in the third decade of April. Mineral fertilizers were applied before sowing, during sowing, as well as 3 times by feeding during the growing season (the first feeding was in the initial phase of budding, the second was during budding, and the third was in the flowering-ripening phase).

For scientific research, the parental forms of cotton varieties Namangan-77, 75007-11 (Australia), Kupaysin, Kelajak, UzFA-705 and line L-500 of medium fiber cotton of the species *G. hirsutum* L. and their hybrids F_1 , F_2 , F_3 obtained with diallelic family crosses, new lines, as well as the L-500 line (currently UzFA-713 variety).

Classical methods of genetics and cotton selection, various genotypic forms crossing methods, as well as comparative morphology and phenological observations, hybridological and genetic-statistical analysis were used. All plants of the studied varieties and their F_1 , F_2 , F_3 generations, families and lines were grown under the same conditions, adhering to randomization, hybridological and statistical variance analyzes

were applied. The data were statistically processed according to B.P. Dospekhov (1985). In F_1 plants, the degree of dominance (hp) was determined by the Wright formula (Beil and Atkins, 1965).

$$hp = \frac{MP - F_1}{P - MP}$$

Here, hp - dominance coefficient;

MP - average value of parental forms;

F_1 – hybrid index;

P – best parent index.

In the first hybrid generation, the inheritance of traits is expressed in the following order:

hp = 0 - dominance case was not observed;

$0 < hp < 1$ - partial dominance;

hp = 1 - complete dominance;

hp > 1 - overdominance or heterosis;

Research results and discussion

To assess selection value of the polymorphic and polygenic F_2 hybrids, we studied heritability estimate of economically valuable trait of cotton, such as boll weight in F_2 hybrids. Types of cotton of various origins, such as Namangan-77 (a product of individual selection from natural hybrid of C-6526 genotype population obtained in its turn by crossing 159-f with (05152) punctatum subspecies), Kupaysin (a product of radiation and multiple individual selection), Kelajak (a product made on the basis of L-38 line, obtained by crossing of intraspecific geographically separated L-6161 *G.hirsutum* and Bulgaria *G.hirsutum* 146 breeds), UzFA-705 and UzFA-713 (made by radiation of dry seeds of L-38 line by ^{60}CO gamma-rays and multiple individual selection), and Australian selection 75007-11 breed served as materials for study.

Heritability value in the hybrid combinations by a boll weight, as it can be seen in Table 1, has different variability. In hybrids heritability estimate by size of cotton bolls ranged from 0.18 to 0.53 (from 18 to 53%), indicating that by the size of cotton

boll some hybrid populations undergo significant environmental effect, the others have high heritable character.

Table 1

Heritability estimate a boll weight in F₂ hybrid populations

♀ \ ♂	Namangan - 77	Kupaysin	Kelajak	75007-11	UzFA-705	UzFA-713
Namangan - 77	-	0,44	0,52	0,18	0,33	0,27
Kupaysin	0,50	-	0,41	0,36	0,45	0,36
Kelajak	0,44	0,42	-	0,43	0,44	0,39
75007-11	0,33	0,53	0,48	-	0,38	0,35
UzFA-705	0,31	0,40	0,45	0,30	-	0,38
UzFA-713	0,21	0,46	0,28	0,30	0,35	-

The highest genotypic character of variability by the trait above was demonstrated by hybrid populations 75007-11 x Kelajak (0.48, 48%), Kupaysin x Namangan-77 (0.50, 50%), Namangan -77 x Kelajak (0.52, 52%) and 75007-11 x Kupaysin (0.53, 53%). Effect of genotypes and environment can be seen equal for variability of a boll weight in F₂ hybrids. The environment appeared to mostly affect the size of bolls of Namangan-77 x 75007-11, UzFA-713 x Namangan-77 and Namangan-77 x UzFA-713 with the heritability estimates 0.18 (18%), 0.21 (21%) and 0.27 (27%), respectively. Mean heritability estimates in other hybrid combinations by a boll weight ranged from 0.30 to 0.47 (from 30 to 30 to 47%). Thus, as it can be seen, a boll weight in F₂ hybrids is affected by the environment factors more significantly than by the genetic ones. High heritable variability by the trait above was demonstrated in the hybrid swarms with higher genetic enrichment and adaptability to the environment. Reciprocal differences in the trait heritability estimates can be attributed to the origin of initial parent forms. As a whole, selection by a boll weight is ineffective.

Conclusion

Thus, F₂ hybrids behavior is connected with the environmental effects on manifestation of a trait and with a response of polygenic system of the hybridized forms to specific conditions of cultivation. However, response of polygenic system to the environmental effects in various genotypes is inadequate. This can be confirmed by high typical heritable variability of a boll weight in geographically separated hybrid swarms, where breeds of domestic selection and a breed of nondomestic selection served as the female parent.

REFERENCES

1. Avtonomov V.A. Variability and heritability of traits in hybrids with wild and ruderal cotton breeds. Summary of Candidate's Dissertation (Agriculture), Tashkent, "FAN" publishing house, 1984, p.23
2. Avtonomov V.A., Egamberdiev R. Variability and heritability of traits determining fiber length and outcome in geographically separated F₁ hybrids of *G. barbadense* L. Soil productivity increase (2nd part). Proceedings of National Scientific-Practical Conference. Tashkent, 2007, 263-265.
3. Brewbaker D.A. Agricultural genetics, Moscow, "Kolos" publishing house, 1966, p. 124
4. Simongulyan N.G. Cotton trait combining ability and heritability. Tashkent, "FAN" publishing house 1977, p.61-108
5. Rokitskyi P.F. Biological statistics. Minsk. "Higher school" publishing house, 1973, p. 316.
6. Khotylova L.V., Tarutina L.V. Genotype-environment interaction. Minsk. "Science and technology" publishing house, 1982, 35-63.